

Intellectual Property Services Classification

The Intellectual Property Services Classification (IPSC) defines types of business activities that are executed by companies active in the IP services market. Each main category is divided in several sub-categories.

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100 Legal Services

Services involving legal or law related matters like issue of patents, preparation of patent filing documents and litigation processes.

110 IPR Protection

Process of assuring legal rights to the objects of IPR (e.g. inventions, literary and artistic works, images, logos, designs) by filing applications with Patent & Trademark Offices and Copyright Offices.

111 Patent and Trademark Search

Prior art search and investigation and comparison of existing intellectual property rights and applications regionally and worldwide.

112 Patent Drafting

Services related to the drafting of a description of the invention required for the patent application, i.e. the process of writing the patent description and claims.

113 Application and Renewal of IPR

Applications for IP protection and renewals of IP protection at industrial property offices (e.g. EPO, DPMA, USPTO, JPO).

120 IPR Contracting

The branch of legal services dealing with assisting with formal IP related agreements between parties.

121 Due Diligence

IP related due diligence services prior to IP transactions (e.g. licensing, acquisition, sale).

122 IPR Transaction Support

Negotiations for and draft of IP transactions (e.g. licensing, acquisition, sale of IP rights), and development of legal strategies for IP protection and use.

130 IPR Litigation

A legal proceeding in a court or a judicial contest to determine and enforce IP rights.

131 Non-judicial Proceeding

Legal services lying outside the proceedings in the court (e.g. determination of possible infringement cases, negotiations for extrajudicial settlements).

132 Judicial Proceeding

Legal services associated with the protection of IP in the court (e.g. representation in civil and criminal proceedings of IP owner or alleged infringer of IP rights).

133 Arbitration and Mediation

Legal services covering the arbitration and mediation proceedings (e.g. preparation of claims, and representation of IP owners or alleged infringer of IP rights).

140 IPR-granting

Industrial property offices that grant and renew legal rights to the objects of IP (EPO, DPMA, USPTO, JPO)

150 Standardization

Legal and regulatory services related to standard essential patents (SEP) setting

160 Anti-Trust and Competition Law Enforcement

Services opposing or intended to regulate technology ownership monopolies (a case where almost all IP in a certain field is owned by one company), such as trusts or cartels, especially in the interest of promoting competition. Service that seeks to maintain market competition by regulating anti-competitive conduct by companies regarding the IPR commercialization activities.

200 IP Consulting

Advisory services related to various IP aspects providing professional or expert advice in a particular area such as market specifics for precise industry for patenting, technology and IP roadmaps, and various analyses.

210 IP Portfolio Analysis

Services for assessment of patents.

211 Legal Quality Assessment

Examining the legal strength of patent.

212 IPR Valuation

Determination or estimation the market value for patents or the underlying technology. Includes valuation of patent portfolios and technology.

213 IP Portfolio Landscaping

Assessment services that comprise mapping technology fields and existing patents according to the given patent portfolio and thus estimating its market position.

220 IP Strategy Development

Consulting services for examining the best solutions of IP usage and further development. Includes strategic planning of technology trajectories/technology paths and IP portfolio development.

230 Commercialization Support

Services related to marketing the patented technologies, assistance with creating prototypes, helping to bring the products to the market.

240 Competitive Intelligence

Collection and analysis of IP related data. It is the service of defining, gathering, analyzing, and distributing intelligence about IP, IP holders, IP portfolios and any aspect of the IP environment needed to support executives and managers in making strategic IP decisions for an organization.

241 Industry Analysis

Examining existing competitors and companies involved in IP market.

242 Technology Analysis

Examining patented technologies, their technical details and – requirements for patenting purposes.

243 Patent Analysis

Services related to examining existing patents and drawing conclusions on patenting related information/activities.

250 Prior Art Search through Crowd-Sourcing Platform

Service that allows an organization or an individual to collaborate with a community to find out if a specific technology exists/is patented.

260 Fighting Infringement, Counterfeiting and Piracy

Services specialized on detecting and interfering IP infringements.

261 Infringement Intelligence Service

Services for searching and demonstrating IP infringements.

262 Technical Infringement Analysis (Software/Circuits)

Services that comprise the technical detection of infringements (e.g. through reverse engineering).

263 Infringement Search through Crowd-Sourcing Platform

Service that allows an organization or an individual to collaborate with a community to find out if an organization or inventor has been involved in litigations or not.

264 Collaboration with Customs

Assistance in searching and actively blocking infringed products through cooperation with customs.

265 Technology Development

Service that supports building technological solutions or technology developments that make it difficult to counterfeit.

270 Internationalization Support

Services for supporting internationalization and trade of IP. Includes assistance in finding investors and business partners abroad and also offering any IPR related advice in legal, strategic or politic topics for certain countries (e.g. local patent laws, local technologies and clusters, societal and environmental issues).

300 Matchmaking and Trading

Services related to arrangement of IPR related development needs of companies with available resources. Includes trading of IPR that results in exchange of ownership.

310 Matchmaking

Service of linking IP (development) needs with available resources (including researchers).

311 Onsite Matchmaking Service

Services related to organizing face-to-face matchmaking events. Including conferences or forums created for purpose of connecting IPR (development) needs with available resources.

312 Online Matchmaking Platform

Web-based platforms for services connecting IP (development) needs with available resources.

320 IPR Brokerage

Services related to assisting patent owners in finding licensees, buyers for their IP. Service includes negotiating IP related contracts, IP purchases, – or sales in return for a fee or commission.

330 IPR Scouting

Specific services that help you to find necessary IP. It is a team of IP and technology experts or an expert who observes and recommends new promising IP for acquiring.

340 IPR Auction

A service dedicated to organizing a public sale in which intellectual property or IPR portfolios are sold to the highest bidder.

341 Onsite IPR Auction

Live IP auctions

342 Online IPR Auction

Web-based IP auctions

350 IPR Exchanges

Traded exchanges (whether physical or online locations) similar to the NYSE and NASDAQ where yet-to-be created IP-based financial instruments would be listed and traded much like stocks are today.

360 IPR Sharing

Defensive publishing or platforms where inventions are made public for free usage of the IP.

361 Defensive Publishing

Defensive publishing or platforms where inventions are made public. Disclosing an enabling description and/or drawing of the product, apparatus or method so that it

enters the public domain and becomes prior art.

362 (Online) IPR Pools for Public Use

Platforms for sharing IPR for free.

370 IPR Pooling/Aggregation

The process of scouting and acquiring existing patents.

371 Offensive IPR pooling

The purchasing of patents in order to assert them against companies that would use the inventions protected by such patents (operating companies) and to grant licenses to these operating companies in return for licensing fees or royalties.

372 Defensive IPR Pooling

The purchasing of patents or patent rights to keep such patents out of the hands of entities that would assert them against operating companies.

380 IP-driven M&A Advisory

Services similar to traditional investment banking services where a percentage fee is received from IPR motivated M&A activities. Services advising technology companies in their merger and acquisition (M&A) activities based on the companies IPR portfolio and earning fees based on the value of the entire deal (or apportioned according to the value of the IPR within the deal).

390 Purchase and Sale of IPR

Services that provide assistance with actions that involve exchange of IP ownership.

400 IP Portfolio Processing

Various services related to creation of IP portfolios and partial management processes of the portfolio related to creating revenues out of IP.

410 Document Processing

Services related to assisting with the documentation of patent process / patenting itself

411 Patent and Design Illustration

Services creating visuals of inventions for better marketing and patenting purposes.

412 IP Translation

Services related to assistance of translations of IP documentation.

420 IP Portfolio Management

Services related to outsourcing all IPR portfolio management related decision like updating the valuable patents, collecting royalties and negotiating the terms and conditions of the license agreement with potential licensees.

430 IP Portfolio Administration

Maintenance and renewal of the IP portfolios as well as collecting royalty rates and dealing with licensing.

440 IPR Augmentation

IPR creation, either for creating new technologies by cooperating with other institutions and as a results being the owner (or co-owner) of the patents created out of that process; or developing new technologies and getting patents on them in-house, using own R&D resources.

441 IPR Augmentation through In-House Labs

Developing IPR for augmentation purposes within the institution in order to develop technologies or IPR portfolios.

442 IPR Augmentation through Outsourcing

Services related to IPR creation for augmentation purposes for various organizations by third parties.

450 Licensing IPR

An act of authorization by the licensor to use the technology by the licensee. Services of licensing and advising for licensing, done by service providers e.g. licensing agents.

451 Carrot Licensing

Services executing carrot licensing involve bringing together licensing partners voluntarily. A carrot patent licensing approach is appropriate when the prospective licensee is not practicing the patented invention and is under no compulsion to take a license.

452 Stick Licensing

Services pursuing stick licensing involve to some degree infringement. A stick patent licensing approach is applied when the prospective licensee is already using your patent technology and, thereby, infringing your patent.

500 IPR-related Financial Service

Resource allocation as well as resource management, acquisition and investment. In other words, finance deals with matters related to money and the markets.

510 Management of Investment Products based on IPR

Services similar to traditional venture capital (VC) or private equity firms services, but specializing in spinning out promising non-core IP which has become “stranded” within larger technology companies, or creating joint ventures between large technology companies to commercialize the technology and monetize the associated IP. IP private equity and venture capital firms raise funds from institutional investors such as companies, banks, governments or high net worth individuals, as well as private equity fund managers themselves.

520 Management of Investment Products based on Royalty Liquidation/Streams

Services related to the counsel, assistance and/or providing capital to patent owners performing IPR securitization financing transactions (which resemble the more common mortgage-backed securities).

530 Financing IPR and Innovation Processes

Providing capital for IP creation and aggregation.

531 Private Financing

Related to service of providing private financing for IP owners, either directly or as intermediaries, usually in the form of loans (debt financing), where the security for the loan is either wholly or partially IP assets (i.e., IP collateralization).

532 Public Funding

Similarly to private funding (see 131), government funding to develop further specific technology areas or promote certain technologies.

533 PPP Financing

Similarly to private funding (see 131), composition of public and private funding for IP creation.

540 IPR Litigation Funding

Litigation funders are providing financial means for IPR litigation and particularly patent litigation cases for a fixed fee or percentage on the amount gained from infringing party.

550 IPR Insurance

Intellectual Property Insurance service protects companies for copyright, trademark or patent infringement claims arising out of the company's operation. It pays the defense costs and any judgment up to the policy limits.

551 IPR Litigation Insurance for Inventors

Insurances focused on inventors that cover legal fees for claiming and litigating own intellectual property rights. IP coverage helps pay the legal expenses of suing an individual or firm that has violated your intellectual property rights.

552 IPR Litigation Insurance for Third-parties

Insurances that cover legal fees related to IPR litigation. Third party coverage protects the client in case of infringing on another party's intellectual property rights and it usually funds legal defense costs for the client.

600 IP-related Communication Service

The collective communication outlets or tools that are used to store and deliver information on IPR related topics or data, like publications, journals, blogs and educational materials. Additionally, the correspondents of IPR related issues like unions and IP interest groups.

610 IP-related Education and Publishing

Services based on specialized education and publishing of IP related topics and non-academic publishers specialized in IP topics.

611 IP-related Education

Services based on specialized IP education and publishing of IP related topics.

612 IP-related Publication

(Online) Journals focusing on IPR related topics. Includes internet blogs.

613 E-learning Solutions for IP

Internet-based education and online courses about intellectual property rights and related issues.

614 Organization and Execution of Meetings specialized on IP Topics

Gatherings or meetings for IP consultation, exchange of IP related information, or discussion, especially ones with a formal agenda on IP related topics.

615 IP-related Scientific Research

Scientific research and publications in the fields of intellectual property (mostly in an economic or legal perspective).

620 IP Software

Various IT solutions and data stored electronically and created for processing and evaluating patents and IP related features.

621 In-House IP Portfolio Management Software

Software for Managing IP Portfolio (e.g. Licensing and collecting of royalties, Application and Renewal support, IP decision management or IP portfolio related business intelligence solutions)

622 IPR Portfolio Management Software for Attorneys

Specialised IP Portfolio Management software for patent attorneys.

623 IP Valuation Software

Software that values or supports valuation of patents and/or portfolios.

624 IPR Search Software

Software or web-based platforms for searching patent databases (EPO, DPMA, USPTO, JPO). Includes further examining and monitoring of patent databases and providing patent information.

625 Patent-based Public Stock Indexing

Stock indexes that are based on aggregated patent and technology value.

630 Patent Databases

Service related to organized collection of IPR related data, today typically in digital form. The data are typically organized to model relevant aspects of patents, intellectual property, and protected technology in a way that supports processes requiring patent related information.

631 Providing Patent Document Data

Services related to collecting data on patents.

632 Providing Data about IP Litigation

Services related to collecting data on patent law cases.

633 Official Design, Patent and Trademark Data provided by Industrial Property

and Trademark Offices

Official design, trademark and patent databases.

640 IP-centric HR Service

Headhunting and scouting services specialised on persons in the field of intellectual property. It includes services that help to recognize outstanding inventors among other IP community members, HR recruitment platforms and conferences on IP related topics for HR people for networking purposes.

641 Matching IP Professionals and Companies through Online Platforms

642 Matching IP Professionals and Companies as HR Agency

650 Interest Group, Political Work

Organisations with IPR related political or legal strategies as main topic. Excludes associations of IP professionals.

660 Association of IP Professionals

Networks and associations of professionals with business or academic interest in IP. Includes academic research groups and bar associations.